

Using AS-units to Measure the Syntactic Complexity of Students' Responses to Epistemic Questions in Algerian EFL Classrooms

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Abstract

The study aims to gauge the syntactic complexity embedded in Algerian EFL students' responses to epistemic questions. It involves an empirical inquiry that employs quantitative methods for answering the research questions and for testing the hypotheses. The main objectives are to determine the average score of syntactic complexity entrenched in students' oral spontaneous production and to probe the significance of the difference existing between the mean scores of complexity elicited by referential and display questions (epistemic questions). Measuring syntactic complexity is based on the implementation of "analysis of speech units" (AS-units) into the examination of transcribed data corresponding to six EFL lessons delivered to third-grade students at two different Algerian universities. The results are derived from the analysis of 437 responses to epistemic interrogatives. The findings indicated that the average score of complexity embedded in the examined responses is equal to 0.56 which means that most of the answers did not involve clausal formations but were rather composed of phrasal and elliptical structures, indicating a tendency toward generating fragmented and concise responses. A very significant difference (p -value= .01) is found to be present between the syntactic complexity of students' answers produced after display/referential questions, as a small to moderate effect size is reported vis-à-vis the impact of the epistemic nature (referential/display) of questions on complexity scores (Cohen's d = 0.35). The main findings of the study imply that referential questions were more effective than their display counterparts in increasing the syntactic complexity of students' oral production as the discrepancy in the complexity of output produced after the two questioning techniques can be noticeable. These insights can guide EFL teachers in selecting efficient questioning techniques that promote language development and better learning outcomes. Further research is warranted in the local context to delve deeper into the underlying mechanisms that govern EFL production and explore other potential factors that might have influenced the observed differences in syntactic complexity.

Keywords: Epistemic questions, display questions, referential questions, syntactic complexity, analysis of speech units, students' oral production.

1. Introduction

Every language practitioner is charged with developing a set of research procedures that will allow him/her to spot the techniques that can ensure a better learning process for learners. Such a task can be easily maintained by designing a methodology that would promote tracking the changes which occur in the oral or written production of learners subsequent to specific teaching strategies. Since language learning achievements are proven to be partially dependent on the teaching techniques that language partitioners apply inside the classroom (e.g. Long, 1983), it would be consequently reasonable to identify which techniques might lead to better learning outcomes in light of the context under which the learning process is taking place. This will eventually help in building a theoretical understanding that is not only informed by foreign conceptions about what could lead to better learning but also by actual contextualised inquiries and the consequent insights that teachers would gain from exploring a wide range of different factors anchored within the teaching-learning process. Thus, the role of the teacher is supposed to be about delivering the lesson's content as well as exploring the variables perceived to have a direct impact on the learning process (e.g. Fareh & Saeed, 2011). That is to say, being able to maintain both the roles of a teacher and a researcher is crucial for any language practitioner who wants to increase the learners' potential for achieving a higher proficiency level.

Since the role of language output has been proven to have a causal relationship with the outcomes of learning (Ellis, 2015; Ortega, 2008; Swain, 1985; 1995), this paper will seek to identify the impact of certain teaching practices on the oral production of students. This can be attained in one way through the examination of the impact of teachers' epistemic questions on the quality of students' language output. More specifically, the study will aim at identifying the effects of display and referential questions on the syntactic complexity of the consequent responses which are expected to be generated following these two categories of questions. The rationale behind exploring the syntactic complexity of output stems from perceiving complexity as being partially responsible for the achievements of learners in language learning (Housen & Kuiken, 2009). This claim has been repeatedly highlighted in literature in the last three decades (Skehan, 1998; Ellis, 2003). Yet, there is a research gap in the local context of Algeria regarding the impact of questioning techniques on the syntactic complexity of EFL students. To our best knowledge, only a few studies have been carried out

in Algeria to explore the impact of functional questions on variables related to EFL learning like the length, accuracy and complexity of language output (e.g. Gouider, 2022a, 2022b; Gouider & Ameziane, 2022; Gouider & Ameziane 2023)

Based on the previous theoretical considerations, this study will attempt to answer the following questions:

- 1- What are the average syntactic complexity scores of students' language output following epistemic questions?
- 2-What is the epistemic category that can lead to higher scores of syntactic complexity in EFL classrooms?

The following null/alternative hypotheses are put forward:

$-H_0$ (null): There is no significant difference between the average scores of syntactic complexity corresponding to display and referential questions in EFL classrooms.

$-H_1$ (alternative): There is a significant difference between the average scores of syntactic complexity corresponding to display and referential questions in EFL classrooms.

This research paper will initially explore the theoretical frameworks and tenets that drove this researcher to examine the actual theme. More specifically, it highlights the fundamental task of teachers represented in conducting classroom research as a key practice for the improvement of the quality of teaching. Also, it sheds light on the importance of following an eclectic approach designed to accommodate the learning contexts and learners' needs to ensure better outcomes in the acquisition of target languages. Subsequently, the present researcher will elaborate on the methodology, including the used instruments and procedures and then the attained findings will be presented and discussed. A general conclusion will be provided at the end of the research paper.

1. 1. The Research Role of Language Educators

Over the last three decades, it has been recognized that the dichotomy separating theory from practice should be rejected because of realising that theory is often "context-free" and detached from the practical issues of everyday teaching (Prabhu, 1990; Kumaravadivelu, 2001; Brown, 2001; Nunan, 1991). Currently, language teachers are considered responsible for setting theories that account for those variables embedded in their courses and in the particular context within which their practice is taking place (Grenfell, 1997). Obviously, to be valid, those theories that teachers form about the teaching-learning process must be

subjected to research, put into action, and then constantly tested throughout practice as the acts of theorising, researching and practising are inseparable ingredients in the professional conduct of a language educator (Brown, 2014).

Stern (1983) considered the theories held by practitioners to be implicit by default but they can be detected based on the assumptions underlying practice, the way a course is planned, the nature of classroom routines and value judgement about instruction along with the everyday decisions that teachers have to make during the lessons' delivery. Thus, theories formed by teachers refer to those assumptions or convictions that govern the actions manifested in their planning and conduction of a course. According to Brown (2014), every teacher is both a practitioner and a theorist, and therefore, all teachers are charged with building a broadly based conceptualisation of the process of language learning and teaching. He points out further that they are all responsible for understanding as much as they can about how to create suitable contexts for optimal acquisition among learners. Whenever that understanding calls for putting together diverse bits and pieces of knowledge, teachers are doing some theory-building (Brown, 2014).

Besides the theories which teachers already have, as reflected in their planning and conduction of routine activities, teachers can construct new theories in order to unravel the sources of unexpected behaviours that may show up in the classroom. These mysteries that might be encountered by the language practitioner can take the form of an unexpected learning behaviour, a surprising turn of classroom events, or any other deviation from the original plan of the lesson (see Harmer, 2007). Whenever a new theory is formed, it must be subjected to scientific research in order to link it with relevant axiomatic beliefs or pieces of evidence belonging to the same field of inquiry. If adequate information is found, the teacher will have further insights about the spotted issue, and he can even anticipate to some extent whether the formed theory is valid or not. Hence, research has a prominent role in helping language educators to obtain a better understanding of the learning process, and consequently improve their teaching practices (Brown, 2014). Also, by carrying out research teachers will provide distinct, targeted observations about the events that occur in local classrooms, and generate context-sensitive hypotheses and research questions. Finally, the new insights derived from research can contribute meaningfully to controversies on theoretical accounts of language learning and help in developing effective curricula designed specifically to be compatible with the local context (Anderson & Rogan, 2011).

Just as students can improve their learning through trial and error, teachers also can improve their teaching by building theories and testing their applicability through practice. In other words, teachers can put this research-supported theory into practice to confirm or disconfirm its feasibility based on practical and empirical terms. In this final phase, the teacher's task is represented in manipulating the classroom setting and activities so that they fall in line with the created theory which is presumed to yield positive outcomes. The success or failure of the applied theory in meeting its desired outcomes will determine whether it is valid or not.

1.2. A Post-method Era

The profession of foreign language teaching has, at last, reached a post-method era where both researchers and practitioners recognise that the diversity of language learners requires an eclectic blend of tasks and activities, each designed for particular learners studying in particular contexts. In other words, it has been realised that "there is no best method" (Prabhu, 1990, p. 161). Currently, it is considered imperative for teachers to be equipped with an active sense of plausibility that will allow them to carry out context-sensitive methodologies that suit the local situation in which their practice of foreign language teaching takes place (Kumaravadivelu, 2001). It is important to note, that for this new trend to be effective, it must be based on a well-informed theoretical understanding that accounts for the principles and the different intertwined variables that govern the teaching-learning process (Brown, 2001).

Since the 1990s, there has been a consensus among scholars that the practice of adopting one method and following it slavishly will not serve the learning process. Instead, post-method teachers "adapt" their foreign language practice in accordance with local contextual factors, while simultaneously being guided by a number of principles (Kumaravadivelu, 1994). In this context, it is stated that "there never was, and probably never will be a method for all" (Nunan, 1991, p. 228). Indeed, the emphasis has been recently directed toward "developing classroom activities which are consonant to what we know about second language acquisition and which are in keeping with the dynamics of the classroom itself" (Nunan, 1991, p. 228). The claim that there is no best method was first discussed by Prabhu in 1990 under three main explanations:

A- Different methods are best for different contexts.

B- All methods are partially true or valid.

C- The notion of a good and a bad method is itself misguided (Prabhu, 1990, p. 161).

The first argument that different methods are best for different contexts would also imply that some methods are inappropriate for particular contexts. That is to say, it depends on “whom the method is for, in what circumstances, for what purposes and so on” (Prabhu, 1990, p. 162). In fact, it has become evident that if a teacher wants to implement a method presupposed to be yielding positive effects on the learning process but in practice learners show a lethargic attitude, disinterest, oppositional behaviour or constant resistance toward it, the method would probably have counterproductive effects on the learning process (e.g. Miller, 2015). For instance, though communicative language teaching (CLT) is considered an accepted norm for foreign language teaching, it may fail to meet its desired outcomes in contexts where learners believe that they are not responsible for their learning and that the job of the teacher is not to act as a facilitator and a guide, but rather as a source of knowledge and an authority figure (Hu, 2002). Thus, there is no universal method that can cater to every learner, accommodate all situations and encompass the diverse array of global contexts.

The second argument, used by Prabhu to support his claim, is that all methods are partially true or valid, which suggests that every method has its own strengths and weaknesses. For example, the grammar-translation method is now discredited and believed to be unproductive if implemented in the classroom, but some of its techniques, like translating from the target to the native language, can be successfully used in explaining the abstract meaning of foreign words (Kong, 2011), such as: hope, despair; time, happiness...etc. In a similar way, although the total physical response (TPR) is a method that can achieve positive outcomes when used to teach children, it would be ineffective and inconvenient for students with an advanced proficiency level (Widodo, 2005). Since every method has its own pros and cons, it is indeed not daring to say that every method is partially true or valid.

As a third argument, Prabhu states that the notion of a good and a bad method is itself misguided. It is unreasonable to attempt to draw a distinction based on presumptions about which method is good or bad. Instead, the evaluation of language teaching is better achieved by distinguishing between “real” and “mechanical” teaching, and relatively whether the

teacher's sense of plausibility is active or not (Prabhu, 1990). Teachers' sense of plausibility represents their subjective understanding of how language learning takes place, and how teaching causes or supports it (Prabhu, 1990). In other words, it is the teacher's general conceptualisation of how teaching leads to desired learning. It is responsible for the choices and decisions that teachers make when deciding on which method or technique to be used in the classroom. When teachers' sense of plausibility is active, the teaching process will be "real" flexible, dynamic, and context-sensitive, while an inactive (frozen) sense of plausibility will lead to "mechanical", "over-routinised" teaching in which lessons settle on a very regular routine without any change, variation or any account for the learners' needs, interests, learning styles, and other related factors (Prabhu, 1990). Finally, it is important to note that teachers' sense of plausibility and conceptualisation of the teaching-learning process, need to be based on a well-informed theoretical understanding (a consistent philosophy) that accounts for the principles and variables of foreign language teaching and learning (Brown, 2001; Kumaravadivelu, 1994).

In a nutshell, the profession of foreign language teaching has reached a post-method era where teachers no longer adopt one method and follow it blindly, but rather adapt the method itself to the learners' needs and the learning context (Can, 2009; Chen, 2014; Galante, 2014; Kumaravadivelu, 2006). Therefore, it is crucial for teachers to dispel the myth presuming the existence of a best method, and instead, develop a principled and eclectic approach to foreign language teaching.

1.3. Measuring syntactic complexity based on AS-units

The process of second and foreign language learning is characterised by the interplay of many factors that can either impede or promote the process of acquisition. During the last four decades, there has been a consensus regarding the importance of learners' output in the process of acquisition (Ellis, 2015; Ortega, 2008; Swain, 1985; 1995). The language output produced by learners is not only essential for acquisition but can also act as a window through which language researchers can track the trajectory of development that learners go through in their course of acquiring new language forms. Typically, oral and written performance allows researchers to spot the gaps and deficiencies that exist in the interlanguage repertoire of learners. Oral performance can be assessed from three main perspectives, namely: fluency,

accuracy and complexity (Housen & Kuiken, 2009). In this study, the focus is directed toward the third dimension which embodies the complexity of the generated output.

Complexity is defined as follows: "Syntactic complexity (syntactic maturity or linguistic complexity) refers to the range of forms that surface in language production and the degree of sophistication of such forms" (Ortega, 2003, p. 492). An analysis of speech unit (AS-unit) is defined as "a single speaker's utterance consisting of an independent clause, or sub-clausal unit, together with any subordinate clause(s) associated with either" (Foster et al., 2000, p. 365). The frequency of subordination in AS-unit can determine the complexity of students' production. For example, if every AS-unit in an observed lesson would contain one or more clauses, a complexity score equal to or higher than the value "1" is going to be obtained. On the other hand, if most of the students' responses would consist of utterances or elliptical articulations, the obtained complexity score would range from a value of "0" to "1".

2. Methodology

2.1. Research Design

The present study involves an empirical research that seeks to explore the complexity of students' answers following teachers' epistemic questions and to find out whether there is an association between the functions of questioning technique and the syntactic complexity of responses. The ex-post facto design was exploited because the observed variables occurred naturally, as they did not necessitate the intervention of the researcher or the manipulation of variables. The participants were composed of six EFL teachers and 108 third-grade students. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were implemented in the analysis of data. It is worth noting that the examined corpus was used by the same author in other studies for different research objectives.

2.2. Research instruments and procedures

The data collection procedure took place at the departments of English of two Algerian universities. It involved a classroom observation of six lessons targeted at third-grade students with six different EFL teachers. Purposive convenience sampling was adopted in the selection of classes. The process of observation involved the use of audio tapes and taking notes in real-time after getting permission from the administrative staff of the two universities and the participants. The audio recordings were later on used to transcribe data. Data coding of

epistemic questions was issued with respect to the taxonomy of Long and Sato (1983). The syntactic complexity of responses was conducted based on AS-units drawing on the work of Foster et al. (2000). Syntactic complexity was measured based on the number of clauses embedded in AS-units across the observed classrooms (see Foster & Wigglesworth, 2016). That is to say, the complexity ratios were based on dividing the number of clauses, generated following every epistemic question, by the number of AS-units comprising the same student's response:

$$\frac{\text{Clause}(s) \text{ of Response } X}{\text{AS - unit}(s) \text{ of Response } X} = \text{Syntactic Complexity of Response } X$$

It should be noted that only those epistemic questions that received verbal answers from students were accounted for in determining the scores of complexity corresponding to display and referential questions. When a question received multiple answers from different students, the complexity of each response was coded separately. Subsequently, the complexity scores belonging to each response (e.g. Response A= 0.5; Response B= 1; Response C= 0) were compiled into the dataset according to the epistemic category of questions (referential/display) which led to their generation. SPSS version 28 represented the statistical software package based on which descriptive and inferential statistics were computed. An independent samples t-test is employed to test the plausibility of the postulated hypotheses and a p-value of .05 ($p \leq .05$) is set as a threshold of statistical significance for testing the research hypotheses. Confidence intervals and effect sizes are also incorporated in this study to gauge the significance of results and to probe the magnitude of the effect brought about by the functional nature of questions on the syntactic complexity of output.

3. Research Findings

Descriptive statistics were used for the purpose of answering the first and the second research questions: "1-What are the average syntactic complexity scores of students' language output following epistemic questions?" and "2-What is the epistemic category that can lead to higher scores of syntactic complexity in EFL classrooms?". The aim was therefore to determine the average syntactic complexity scores pertaining to referential/display questions and to conclude which category can lead to more complex responses. The results showed that the complexity mean of referential questions was equal to 0.84 compared to a value of 0.53 for display questions. The standard deviation reported with referential questions (SD=0.31)

was higher than that of display questions (SD= 0.08). The previous results are based on the analysis of 437 verbal responses to epistemic interrogatives, as displayed in table 1:

Table 1. Descriptive statistics related to the average scores of syntactic complexity elicited by epistemic (referential/display) questions

Measured Variable	Questions	N of Students' Responses/Turns			
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	
Syntactic Complexity	Referential Questions	101	.78	1.09	.11
	Display Questions	336	.50	.71	.04
	Epistemic Questions	437	.56	.82	.04

The earlier results indicate that the syntactic complexity scores of referential questions were generally higher than those corresponding to display questions. That is to say, there is a numerical difference between the complexity scores of the two epistemic categories. The higher standard deviation corresponding to referential questions implies that the complexity scores have a higher deviation from the obtained mean in comparison to the display category.

To test the significance of the aforementioned numerical difference, this researcher made use of an independent samples t-test. To start with, results from Leven's test for equality of variances were initially checked to ensure that the variability of the analysed values (complexity scores) were similar or different across the two groups (display/referential) of the independent dichotomous variable (epistemic questions). The concerned statistics implied that the assumption of homogeneity of variances was violated ($p < .001$) and for this reason equality of variances was not assumed ($F= 20.50, p < .001$). As a consequences, results from the Welch t-test were adopted. The findings showed the presence of a very significant difference ($p = .01$) between the mean scores of syntactic complexity of referential and display questions [$t(126.51) = 2.49, p = .01, 95\% CI = .06, .51$]. The findings are displayed in the following table:

Table 2. Independent Samples Test and Levene's test

		Levene's Test		t-test for Equality of Means							
		F	Sig.	t	Df	Significance				95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
Syntactic complexity	Equal variances assumed	20.50	<.001	3.10	435.00	.00	.00	.29	.09	.10	.47
	Equal variances not assumed			2.49	126.51	.01	.01**	.29	.12	.06	.51

Note. ** very significant

The previous findings imply that referential questions have a statistically higher potential to stimulate more complex responses compared to display questions since the observed disparity in the average complexity scores is very unlikely to be due to chance. Therefore, The results indicate a significant departure from the null hypothesis, supporting the alternative hypothesis instead. In other words, there is a statistical difference between the average complexity scores elicited by display and referential questions.

Moreover, Cohen's d was used to measure the effect size of the results displayed earlier. The statistical findings suggest the existence of a small to moderate effect size [d= 0.35, 95% CI= .13, .58]. This entails that the difference can be noticeable despite that the nature of epistemic questions might not be very substantial in affecting the complexity of output. The results are displayed below along with other complementary measures:

Table 3. Independent samples Effect sizes

	Effect Size Measures	Standardizer	Point Estimate	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower	Upper
Syntactic complexity	Cohen's d	.81	.35	.13	.58
	Hedges' correction	.81	.35	.13	.57
	Glass's delta	.71	.40	.18	.63

4. Conclusion

This study aimed at exploring the syntactic complexity of students' language output following display/referential questions and to identify whether there is a significant difference between the complexity scores that correspond to the two mentioned categories. The results showed that referential questions have a higher potential to elicit more complex responses than display questions. The findings imply that most of the students' responses were not

embedded with clauses but rather with sub-clausal units that consist of elliptical utterances, or minor utterances which can be labelled as “non-sentences” or “irregular sentences” (Quirk, et al., 1985). The syntactic complexity of the spontaneous production of students was low since the average score corresponding to display questions was 0.50 (Av. score= 0.50) and that of referential questions represented a value of 0.78 (Av. score= 0.78). The difference between the average scores corresponding to display/ referential questions was found to be statistically significant [$p= .01$, 95% CI= .06, .51] with a small to medium effect size [$d= 0.35$, 95% CI= .13, .58]. That is, the functional nature of epistemic questioning techniques can have a noticeable effect on the level of syntactic complexity manifested in students' oral production. The findings suggest that Algerian EFL teachers should rely more on referential questions to increase the syntactic complexity of students' language output, which can lead in turn to the improvement of learning outcomes. Eventually, it should be noted that the present study represents the first research endeavour, in the Algerian context of EFL teaching, to examine the syntactic complexity of oral production based on the incorporation of AS-units. More empirical studies are still needed in the local context to attain more comprehensive findings and enhance our understanding of the subject matter.

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Appendix: Supplementary Descriptive Statistics about the Dataset

Epistemic Questions		Statistic	Std. Error	
Syntactic Complexity	Referential Questions	Mean	.78	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean		
		Lower Bound	.57	
		Upper Bound	1.00	
		5% Trimmed Mean	.65	
		Median	.00	
		Variance	1.19	
		Std. Deviation	1.09	
		Minimum	.00	
		Maximum	4.00	
		Range	4.00	
		Interquartile Range	1.00	
		Skewness	1.55	.24
		Kurtosis	1.73	.48
	Display Questions	Mean	.50	.04
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean			
	Lower Bound	.42		
	Upper Bound	.57		
	5% Trimmed Mean	.42		
	Median	.00		
	Variance	.50		
	Std. Deviation	.71		
	Minimum	.00		
	Maximum	3.00		
	Range	3.00		
	Interquartile Range	1.00		
	Skewness	1.35	.13	
	Kurtosis	1.27	.27	